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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ABHIMANYU A bearing USN6SU21CV001 has completed his/her internship at Manipal Hospital Mysore in the first Semester of the Cardio Vascular technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ABIN A bearing USN6SU21CV002 has completed his/her internship at Manipal Hospital Mysore in the first Semester of the Cardio Vascular technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ADWAITH C bearing USN6SU21CV003 has completed his/her internship at Manipal Hospital Mysore in the first Semester of the Cardio Vascular technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms AKHIL V KUMAR bearing USN6SU21CV004 has completed his/her internship at Manipal Hospital Mysore in the first Semester of the Cardio Vascular technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms ALEENA THOMAS bearing USN6SU21CV005 has completed his/her internship at Manipal Hospital Mysore in the first Semester of the Cardio Vascular technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms ARSHAD AHAMMED bearing USN6SU21CV006 has completed his/her internship at Manipal Hospital Mysore in the first Semester of the Cardio Vascular technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms ASHIKA ULLAS C K bearing USN6SU21CV007 has completed his/her internship at Manipal Hospital Mysore in the first Semester of the Cardio Vascular technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ASIF NOUSHAD bearing USN6SU21CV008 has completed his/her internship at Manipal Hospital Mysore in the first Semester of the Cardio Vascular technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms AVANTHIKA VINILKUMAR bearing USN6SU21CV009 has completed his/her internship at Manipal Hospital Mysore in the first Semester of the Cardio Vascular technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms AZIL BIN ASHRAF K bearing USN6SU21CV010 has completed his/her internship at Manipal Hospital Mysore in the first Semester of the Cardio Vascular technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms BINSHA BASHEER PANIKAVEETTIL bearing USN6SU21CV011 has completed his/her internship at Manipal Hospital Mysore in the first Semester of the Cardio Vascular technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms HAMDA NOWSHAD bearing USN6SU21CV012 has completed his/her internship at Manipal Hospital Mysore in the first Semester of the Cardio Vascular technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms HANS FERDINAND D SOUZA bearing USN6SU21CV013 has completed his/her internship at Manipal Hospital Mysore in the first Semester of the Cardio Vascular technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms JITHIN SUDHAKAR bearing USN6SU21CV014 has completed his/her internship at Manipal Hospital Mysore in the first Semester of the Cardio Vascular technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms JOSHNA SHAJI bearing USN6SU21CV015 has completed his/her internship at Manipal Hospital Mysore in the first Semester of the Cardio Vascular technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms MARIYAM RUMAIZA bearing USN6SU21CV016 has completed his/her internship at Manipal Hospital Mysore in the first Semester of the Cardio Vascular technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms MASOODH M bearing USN6SU21CV017 has completed his/her internship at Manipal Hospital Mysore in the first Semester of the Cardio Vascular technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms MOHAMMED FAIZ H bearing USN6SU21CV018 has completed his/her internship at Manipal Hospital Mysore in the first Semester of the Cardio Vascular technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms MOHAMMED SADHUL bearing USN6SU21CV019 has completed his/her internship at Manipal Hospital Mysore in the first Semester of the Cardio Vascular technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms NANDANA BABU bearing USN6SU21CV020 has completed his/her internship at Manipal Hospital Mysore in the first Semester of the Cardio Vascular technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms NUSAIR SIDDIQUE bearing USN6SU21CV021 has completed his/her internship at Manipal Hospital Mysore in the first Semester of the Cardio Vascular technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms PRAJNA S SHETTIGAR bearing USN6SU21CV022 has completed his/her internship at Manipal Hospital Mysore in the first Semester of the Cardio Vascular technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms ROHITH P K bearing USN6SU21CV023 has completed his/her internship at Manipal Hospital Mysore in the first Semester of the Cardio Vascular technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms SAFA ALI bearing USN6SU21CV024 has completed his/her internship at Manipal Hospital Mysore in the first Semester of the Cardio Vascular technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms SAFUWA PERWIN bearing USN6SU21CV025 has completed his/her internship at Manipal Hospital Mysore in the first Semester of the Cardio Vascular technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms SHABEEBA PUTHANVEETIL bearing USN6SU21CV026 has completed his/her internship at Manipal Hospital Mysore in the first Semester of the Cardio Vascular technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms SIVARANJINI B bearing USN6SU21CV027 has completed his/her internship at Manipal Hospital Mysore in the first Semester of the Cardio Vascular technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms SREYA M M bearing USN6SU21CV028 has completed his/her internship at Manipal Hospital Mysore in the first Semester of the Cardio Vascular technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms VISHANTH V AMEEN bearing USN6SU21CV029 has completed his/her internship at Manipal Hospital Mysore in the first Semester of the Cardio Vascular technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms VYSHAKH U bearing USN6SU21CV030 has completed his/her internship at Manipal Hospital Mysore in the first Semester of the Cardio Vascular technology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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